

Code Book - Categories		
Caique G. Moreira, Breno B. N. de França, Tayana U. Conte		
This document is a supplementary material of the paper “Analyzing the BizDev Interface in an Enterprise Context: A Case of Developers Acting in Business” by Caique G. Moreira, Breno B. N. de França, and Tayana U. Conte. Here, we provide the part of our codebook that contains the categories.		
	ID	Super Category
	superCat1	Facilitating factors for technology area to act in business
	superCat2	Good BizDev communication facilitating technology area to act in business
	superCat3	Bad BizDev communication affecting negatively technology area to act in business
	superCat4	Motivation and opportunities on BizDev communication
	superCat5	Process Reengineering Project bringing improvements to BizDev communication and facilitating technology area to act in business.
	superCat6	Characteristics that define how the IT sector acts in business.
	superCat7	Isolated and joint actions with the business sector: Two facets of IT act in business.
ID	Super Categoria	Category
cat1	superCat1	Culture of the company influencing IT sector employees to get involved with business
cat2	superCat1	Members of the technology sector having knowledge about business
cat3	superCat1	Efforts to bring Development and Business teams closer together
cat4	superCat1	Environment/ecosystem encouraging/facilitating IT employees to get involved with business
cat5	superCat2	Efforts to continuously improve BizDev communication
cat6	superCat2	Company environment/structure providing good BizDev communication
cat7	superCat2	Members of the business sector having knowledge about technology
cat8	superCat2	High frequency of communication in the BizDev interface
cat9	superCat2	BizDev communication without friction/barriers
cat10	superCat3	Company environment/structure providing bad BizDev communication
cat11	superCat3	Business sector members with little knowledge about technology
cat12	superCat3	Impediments and barriers in BizDev communication
cat13	superCat3	Low frequency of communication between teams in the BizDev interface
cat14	superCat3	Misalignment and noise in BizDev communication
cat15	superCat3	Varying levels of BizDev communication skills among IT employees: analysts tend to communicate worse in the interface than higher positions
cat16	superCat4	Reasons for BizDev Communication
cat17	superCat4	Improvement Opportunities for BizDev Communication
cat18	superCat5	Process Reengineering Project
cat19	superCat5	Product Manager role acting on the BizDev interface
cat20	superCat5	Reengineering project brought an increase in transparency and democratization of the decision-making process
cat21	superCat6	Technology team working on prioritizing/re-prioritizing requirements/tasks.
cat22	superCat6	Technology team working on a data driven behavior
cat23	superCat6	Technology team working on requirements/directions definition
cat24	superCat6	Consequences of technology team's act in requirements/directions definition
cat25	superCat6	Disagreements about business directions between Technology and Business areas
cat26	superCat7	Development teams acting in business individually and isolatedly
cat27	superCat7	Poorly structured, unclear, and undemocratic decision-making/ideation process
cat28	superCat7	Technology department acting in business in conjunction with the Business department